

Rurbanization it's Advantages and Disadvantages

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ABSTRACT

Rurbanisation is new concept which has more importance in developing the rural areas with the assimilation of urban facilities. Rurbanisation can cater the needs of rural people with better facilities and infrastructure. It has it's advantages empowering the rural people with the facilities like electrification which has the major utility in Agricultural sector of rural areas. It also has some drawbacks as lack of political will, Delay in funds disbursement and geographical factors like topography makes it difficult for the implementation of Rurbanisation, mostly in North –East areas.

Keyword: Rurbanization, Assimilation, Disbursement, Topography.

INTRODUCTION

Rurbanization process is the rural areas transform into urban areas. It is highly affected by the geographical, political, environmental, and economic constraints and opportunities. Effective implementation of government schemes facilitates the process of rural transformation.

It aims at urbanization of selected rural clusters (essentially contiguous gram panchayat areas selected by respective state governments) by provision of basic civic amenities like:

1. Mobile health units
2. Provision of drinking water
3. Electrification
4. LPG connections

5. E-governance initiatives that will involve internet connectivity for provision for basic civic services and more.

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to create a big village with an urban feel. This will help in improving the quality of life of people in the rural areas and help to reduce the urban-rural divide which will ultimately reduce the rural to urban migration.

These include,

- It will create a development central hub for a cluster of villages
- Connect all the nearby villages and provide economical support to them
- It will lead to decentralization of activities from rural (through Rurban centres)
- Enhance financial inclusion, infrastructure, social benefits to masses
- Create more accessible markets for farmers' yield
- Encourages participation of private sector by support of government (with critical gap funding)
- Backward states and north eastern states will gain a lot from this.

ORIGIN OF PROBLEM

The concept of Rurbanization is newly emerging in recent decades throughout in world, but india has been taking baby steps to meet its target of to development the rural areas transformation into the

urban areas though Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission scheme. The research intend to focus on advantages and disadvantages of Rurbanization.

METHODOLOGY

The study focuses this area's secondary information collected from various books, magazines, national and international journals, government reports, publication from various websites focuses on the concept of Rurbanization.

ADVANTAGES OF RURBANIZATION

1. It will reduce the rural-urban divide by providing physical and communication connectivity.
2. Reverse migration will be promoted due to the availability of urban amenities and jobs.
3. Purchasing power of rural inhabitants will increase due to employment opportunities.
4. It will help utilize India's demographic dividend since rural inhabitants will have access to skill development centre's.
5. The Smart Cities Mission will receive a boost as the revamped smart cities will not have to bear the burden of rural migration.

DISADVANTAGES OF RURBANIZATION

1. It will require coordination between numerous entities-Union Rural development Ministry, State governments and private sector to succeed.
2. The Rurban clusters will be developed through the Private Public Partnership(PPP) model. However this will lead to an increase in operating costs.
3. Private companies might not be willing to partner the government in developing rurban clusters in areas with law and order issues like J& K and the North East.

CHALLENGES

Already there are several schemes for rural development and this may create overlap and delicacy, so better integration needed.

- Greater involvement of Panchayat Raj Institutions(PRI) needed with bottom up area-specific approach required else it won't generate much development.

- Digital literacy and e-governance will be difficult in the absence of Information Technology Communication (ITC) infrastructure.
- Close coordination between center, state and district needed to make it successful.
- With effective implementation this is a step in right direction.

CONCLUSION

Though Rurbanisation has it's disadvantages in the form of administrative and governance lapses, it has it's advantages in the form of empowering the rural demography. The administrative and governance lapses can be overcome through effective governance. Rurbanisation has a lot of opportunity to boost the economic growth of our country which is a greatest advantage which includes the rural area.

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